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Perspectives of Teachers on Disruptive Behavior of Students in Norwegian Waldorf Schools

Abstract: This article examines the experience and the perception of Norwegian Waldorf school teachers about classroom disruption. Their in-depth understanding about student disruptive behaviors in the classroom and their prevention and intervention strategies are the main area of this investigation. The reviewed literature about classroom disruption from a broader perspective to a narrowed down Norwegian Waldorf context gives a funnel-shape to the existing body of knowledge in this field through this research article. Teachers may apply various strategic methods to prevent classroom disruption based on the context they work in; however, no classroom is completely disruption free. Neither disruption free class is recognized as the best class. Therefore, the classroom teachers need both prevention and intervention strategies against disruptive behaviors in the classroom. Qualitative interpretation was applied, which supported to explore the subjective experience of grades IX and X teachers with their preventative and curative measures against disruption. The themes stemmed from the data have been analyzed using Rudolf Steiner's loved authority of the teacher and Nel Noddings' care with a focus on the ways these theories are operationalized in a particular classroom context to find solutions of disruptions. The findings show that 'personally knowing the students', 'intimate relationship of the teacher with students' and 'care' help the teachers prevent possible disruption and promptly intervene them in the classroom. Further, the results show that students may not always respect the teachers without questioning their authority; instead, due to their higher position, personally knowing the students for a long period of time and their knowledge and maturity, they are in higher order of teacher-student relational hierarchy which eventually helps them maintain order in the classroom.

Keywords: Classroom disruption; teacher-student relationship; prevention; intervention

Introduction

This research study was conducted as the master's thesis of the researcher. It explores the perception and experience of grades IX and X Waldorf school teachers about students' disruptive behaviors in the classroom. Disruptive behavior of the students refers to the general activities or misconduct of the students that often violate the communal sentiment interrupting the teaching-learning activities. This article delimits

the issue of students' disruptive activities in the classroom and its preventive and interruptive measures taken by the concerned on-duty teachers.

Disruptive behavior of the students is a global phenomenon. Pitsoe and Letseka (2014) claim, "Globally, school disciplinary problems and challenges have long been some of the most dismaying and unsettling aspects of education" (p. 1525). School-going students are more likely to be disruptive as they are in the process of exploring the world and society. Therefore, this research study intends to discover the most appropriate ways to resolve such behavior worthy to all the classroom teachers. The findings will certainly help maintain an academic and conducive environment of the school.

An overview of the measures applied to prevent and interrupt the disruptive behaviors of the students shows wider variation from developing to developed countries. In the context of Nepal, "there is no explicit prohibition of corporal punishment in schools in the Education Act 1971 or the Education Regulation 2003" (Global Initiative to End All Corporal Punishment of Children, 2015, p. 3). As a result, reporting of administering corporal punishment in the classroom is frequent. The Norwegian act pertaining to school education says, "Corporal punishment or other humiliating forms of treatment must not be used" (Education Act, 1998, Chapter, 3, Section, 7). But it does not mean that there exist no disruptive behaviors in the school classroom in a country like Norway. "In Norway... disruption is a challenge in schools. However, for reasons that are not obvious, teachers in Norwegian classrooms struggle more than their colleagues in many comparable countries" (Vaaland, 2016, p. 104). Vaaland (2016) further says;

"...identified two main strategies for turning highly disruptive classes around. One was called a cognitive strategy and prioritized step-by-step training and implementation of good classroom organization and management. The other, a system approach, introduced several changes at a time intending to rearrange the distribution of social power in the classroom". (p. 92)

These strategies were recommended by, "...the only informants (who) were the chosen experts" (Vaaland, 2016, p. 52) but experience and perception of the classroom teachers who directly deal with the disruptive students could give a different dimension to the research findings.

Consequently, it is worth researching on the ways the teachers experience and reflect upon the disruption of the students. Also, the research findings about their ways of perceiving the preventive and curative measures to handle the students having such behaviors will certainly be fruitful to the teachers because they directly face it in their daily professional experience in the Norwegian context.

As the research issues anticipate an in-depth understanding of the participants, a qualitative research design is employed to investigate their subjective perception in a particular context. The data corpus consists of open-ended semi-structured interviews and class observation for one week in a Norwegian Waldorf school. Theme analysis of the data has contributed to addressing the research issues raised.

Classroom activities are encompassed as the study area of this research. The delimitation of the issue makes the research report more specific and goal oriented as "it imposes a selection, a structure on what would

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otherwise be an overwhelming mass of information” (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007, p. 193). The findings of this study that help to resolve the issues related to classroom disruption are practical contributions to this field.

Classroom disruption

I want to narrow down my research issues towards the classroom context of the secondary level school. Illuminating the meaning of disruptive behavior of the students in the classroom, Suleman, Hussain and Ambreen (2013) opine;

“Classroom disruption refers to the behavior that a reasonable person would view as substantially or repeatedly obstructing and frustrating the environment of the classroom. Usually, disruptive behavior shows down and negatively affects the instructor’s capability to conduct the class, or the capability of other students to profit from the instruction”. (p. 237)

In other words, they say that the behaviors that make the classroom environment or learning environment problematic and frustrating for a rational person are disruptive behaviors. A teacher has to deliver or transmit certain knowledge to the students in the classroom. If the students’ behaviors repeatedly obstruct the conducive environment, students cannot learn and get expected fruits from the classroom teaching. Further, the capacity of the teacher is also questioned.

Because of its negative impact in the social context, where it takes place, the management or prevention of student disruptive behavior is a crucial component in teacher education and worth researching for achieving optimum benefits from teaching-learning in the classroom. I have reviewed the literature about student disruption and its relational measures.

The relationship between the teacher and the students is a key element to diminish classroom disruption. According to Cullingworth (2014), “This can best be understood as an ‘authoritative’ relationship: caring, nurturing, and accepting, but also demanding. As for knowing when to enact which dimension of this authoritative model, such as when to be demanding and when to be accepting...” (p. 134).

The teacher-student relationship is based on the modality of *care*, love and authority. The most important factor in such a relationship is the timing of being authoritative and caring or loving. It is the responsibility of the teacher when he or she tries to create this balance and rhythm in the relationship.

According to the theoretical standpoint of Noddings, *care* exists in the relationship between the one, who cares and the one, who is cared for. There should be actions and behaviors in the one who cares on behalf of the one who is cared for. These actions may not always be noticeable to the ones who watch from outside. The third person may sometimes explicitly see the caring behaviors. The ones, who care, can feel it from inside, or it is subjective. And it is caused by and accompanied by the feeling of regard (Noddings, 2013).

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Further defining caring Noddings says, “Caring involves stepping out of one's personal frame of reference into the others. When we care, we consider the other’s point of view, his objective needs, and what he expects of us” (Noddings, 2013, p. 24). In other words, the ones, who care have to come out of their personal frame of interest and enter into the others’. They give more preference to others' thoughts and needs rather than their own. They give focus on what the 'cared-for' anticipates from them. Therefore, the reasons for the behaviors of the 'one-caring' depends on the problematic circumstance of the 'cared-for'.

It is worth guiding this review onto what Rudolf Steiner says on the disruptive behavior and discipline of the students in classroom setting because the Waldorf schools use the educational pedagogy propounded by him and my research issues guide me towards the Waldorf classroom. Shedding light on the significance of personally knowing the students Steiner (1995) says, "The treatment of children according to temperament has such an important place in teaching" (p. 63). Until a teacher understands the temperament of the students, he/she cannot deal with anything related to them; and unless a teacher knows the students individually, it is not possible to understand their temperament.

As Steiner presents the significance of the teacher-student relationship in the teaching-learning process, he further sheds light on this issue. When the teachers make way to the hearts of the students reading the temperament, they can manage the sitting place of the students in the classroom in such a way that the students can be easily handled. It helps the teacher maintain his/her superior authority among the students. As a result, due to this unquestioned authority of the teachers, the students naturally comply with the teacher and maintain order. Thus, on the one hand, discipline is maintained; on the other hand, the teacher’s authority remains intact among the students (Steiner, 1995).

As the students grow, they want the teacher's authority to be assured and more justified as 'natural authority'. And this authority is very important in the teaching-learning process because "in childhood, they respected a loved authority with religious veneration" (Steiner, 1996, p. 141). A child honors his or her teacher (*loved-authority*) being just like a devotee to the God.

To sum up, the teacher-student relationship plays a key role to maintain order in the Waldorf classroom. In this relationship, the role of the teacher is always more important as they are the authority and the leader or commander. They maintain this relationship through knowing the students personally and making the students realize that they love and *care* for the students. When the students realize these realities and trust the teacher, the authority of the teacher over the students becomes ‘natural authority’. Consequently, the teachers can prevent and promptly intervene in the disruption in the classroom in a successful way.

The concept of caring deals with the behaviors of the caregiver or 'one-caring', 'cared-for', the relationship between them and how it operates in the relationship. How do the teachers, who care for the students, take the task of *care*? As Steiner said, do the students obey and respect the 'natural authority' of the teacher with 'religious veneration'? What strategic measures do they apply to prevent and intervene in the classroom? Hence, it is a crucial issue to investigate and deal with in empirical research.

Research design and methods

Under qualitative methodology, I have used a basic interpretative approach to address the research questions posed in this research study. The descriptive and non-experimental design has helped investigate the perception of the teachers involved (Savin-Baden and Major, 2013). It applies purposive sampling under the non-probability sampling procedures. Also, this study has used “opportunistic sampling” (Savin-Baden and Major, 2013, p. 315) strategy of purposive sampling.

The respondents of this study are the teachers at lower secondary (*Ungdomsskole*) at Waldorf schools in Norway. I set the criteria of having at least ten-year experience for the informants as they were “knowledgeable people” and a key informant to explore this study (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007, p. 97).

The open-ended interview was the major source of this study (Merriam, 2002, p. 4). To ensure validity, I have used member check/respondent validation (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007).

I have used the basic thematic analysis approach to work with the data and further interpreted the qualitative narrated data as it has the potential to open up novel and unexpected dimensions of the issue (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Findings

This section contains the presentation of data gathered from the key respondents. The narrative versions of the respondents are supported by the expressions and the key thematic coding to reflect upon the disruptive behavior of students at Waldorf schools in Norway.

Interviewee A defines the relationship, particularly a loving relationship, with the students, which can be expressed to them by touching them if they like it. She thinks,

“The most important thing is the relationship. And I have a good relationship like, in my class, I can correct them individually with much *love* and *care*.”

Researcher: Loving and caring relationship?

Informant: Yeah, I *love* them.”

When a teacher personally knows the students, he or she also knows their likes and dislikes. It helps solve any problems related to them and prevent possible challenges they might create in the classroom for maintaining the smooth running of the classroom. From her facial expression, it was clear how loving and caring relationship she maintains with her students. I found that *love* and *care* are interwoven with each other. She loves her students; so, she takes *care* of them.

Reflecting on a case of a disruptive boy student, she claims that she has a *motherly love* for them.

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“Researcher: Motherly relation?”

Informant: Yeah, I think. I have *a lot of love* for him. So, I have to be...so I can give him too much, you know. He is not my son” (interviewee A).

When I raised the matter about *motherly love* to the students, she agrees that she has *motherly love* for these students although they are not her biological children, either.

But the Interviewee B has a different opinion about disruptive students. According to him, some students are too stubborn. Three or four students, in grade X, don't respect the teacher. He says, "...They don't respect the adults."

It shows that some of the students do not have a fair relationship with the teacher because the students do not respect the teacher. Describing those few disruptive students in the class, Interviewee B reiterates, "They have no respect for adults." He expresses distress to "having fun disturbingly" by these students. He thinks these boys are a challenge to him. In such a case, he ignores them.

But sometimes, ignoring the mischievous activities also turns to be a worthy way to correct the students. Interviewee A reflects on a bizarre and interesting event about a student she has experienced in the following narrative;

When I was teaching in the front, he went up; and he took my coat, put on my coat; and he took all my clothes (which she had taken off while teaching), and he sat there. I didn't say anything. I just continued as normal.... I think I had him like three or four months.... So, he started to know me. I had been working on him. He had been a very difficult, very special boy. And when he did this, I felt accepted by him. I felt this was a strong moment. He now shows me a kind of acceptance. And who want to put on others' clothes? I mean the smell of other people. It is very intimate.... But we have now established a relationship. And he started to listen to what I said to and he did what...and he did my work....

This is a unique experience she has gone through. This student does unaccepted works of putting on the clothes of the teacher and sitting in the class during her whole lecture. It might have caused some humour in the classroom. As a result, the lecture could have been disrupted. However, the teacher did not take any action. In the long run, they got a chance to know each other and establish such a relationship, which finally helped both of them for a good classroom environment. It is a beautiful and interesting example of overlooking the mischievous activities of the students and developing a close and healthy relationship with them to address the disruptive behaviors in the classroom. Interviewee A mentions,

“They want to know that I am in charge that I have the power to make them silent.... Can she manage...to keep the class in order and teach me anything?”

Interviewee A elaborates the general behaviors of the pupils to the teachers in the classroom. At the beginning of the class, the students also want to test the teachers whether they can control the class or not; whether they can maintain order and teach them in the classroom. This statement indicates that the relations between the teacher and the students are not always plain in the hierarchy. It goes on fluctuation between them. Sometimes, the students also want to overpower the teacher.

The data claim that students show different types of behaviors that disrupt the class. Some of the students can be controlled relatively in an easy manner with love and care of the teachers and their authority upon them. But it is not always the situation in the class. Sometimes the students might disobey and challenge the authority of the teachers. In such cases, the teacher might ignore them but do not confront them. Such ignore might bring positive results.

Discussion

Interviewee A emphasizes the importance of knowing each other. She knows the students and so do the students to her as she has been teaching them for years. And because of knowing the students personally, it is quite easy for her to handle the students in case of the occurrence of disruptive behaviors in the class. According to interviewee B, this knowing deepens in the teaching-learning process; as a result, the teachers know the learning process of the students and see how they are doing and follow up this process. This knowing is reciprocal. Interviewee B believes that the students also need to know the teachers. The teachers know what they do and how they are doing.

Steiner (1995) confirms that the teacher needs to know the individuality or individual characteristic of the students. If the teacher does not know them individually, they might turn disruptive in the classroom. Therefore, until the teacher knows the temperament of the students, it is difficult to treat them according to their needs.

Knowing is a key element of the teacher-student relationship. When they know each other, the bond of the relationship becomes stronger. Knowing is highly appreciated in the context of Waldorf School or pedagogy. And it becomes a strong foundation for the prevention and intervention of the disruptive behaviors of the students in the classroom.

Knowing each other in the community of teachers and students lays a foundation for the *care* that a teacher does towards the students. Caring for the students by a teacher is a significant aspect of the teacher-student relationship.

As interviewees A and B care for the students, they care for whether the students are doing good in studies or not, their health condition and their overall behaviors. Interviewee B's *care* is more focused on the students' academic aspects, obedience and other mischievous activities. But interviewee A's *care* is more focused on the love and emotional aspects of the students. Noddings (2013) confirms that there exists *care* in the relationship.

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The relationship is formed because of caring. There are some actions when the caregiver cares for somebody. But the action may not be always visible. The interviewee B cares more about the academic progress of the students. The action of interviewee A is visible for all in the classroom. But the caring action of interviewee B might not be visible; however, he is concerned about the academic and behavioral needs of the student during their problematic situation.

During the conscious ignoring when a student was putting on her clothes, interviewee A cares about the student mischievous activities but she does nothing apparently. In this case, the caring actions are not visible. Noddings (2013) says the behavior of the teachers is also changed because of the problematic situation they face. Interviewee B expresses his distress to the students who are disruptive and do not respect the teachers. He ignores such students but consciously.

The students may not always want to be submissive; they also want to check and test the authority of the teacher. This is a dynamic of the execution of authority in the relationship. Unlike Steiner (1996) says, the teacher's authority may not always remain unquestioned and untested by the students.

Interviewee A focuses on how students try to test them. Her experience explored how this hidden aspect of the teacher's authority upon the students in the classroom works. When a student puts on her clothes and sits on the bench, the teacher's authority seems to be at stake. She (interviewee A) 'consciously ignores' it because she neither wants to lose her authority nor be *careless* to the student. But her success to bring the student back on track is due to knowing and developing a relationship with him. The student, who puts her clothes on and sits on his bench tends to have the position of the teacher (authority) in terms of guise.

On the other hand, his intention is not directed to the religious reverence to the teacher; rather it seems that he wants to test the teacher's response to him. The authority of the teacher upon the students prevails in the delicate dynamics of relationships in themselves. Interviewee B also reiterates that some students do not respect the teachers. This also clarifies how the honorary authority of the teacher is sometimes challenged by some students. And authority is not solely rested in the teachers as it is traditionally understood. It is the teachers' responsibility to be sincere in this relationship because he or she is assigned to maintain a conducive environment in the classroom.

Conclusion

The informants' perception is that having a positive and intimate relationship develops trustworthiness between the teacher and the students. In the context of Waldorf school, the system of the class teacher and the class guardian helps the teachers know the individual students and their individuality (Steiner, 1995). In Waldorf schools, the teachers and the students form a community, where they know and help each other. If the teachers do not know the individuality of the students, they might turn disruptive in the classroom. Therefore, it is important to know the temperament of the students, so that, the teachers can prevent and promptly intervene in the students' disruptive behaviors.

Noddings (2013) states that the ones who are cared for need to realize that they are being cared for. When a student puts on the clothes of the teacher and sits on the bench listening to her lecture, she consciously ignores it, showing no apparent action. However, she is still caring about the activities of the students. Interviewee B's *care* for the academic progress of the students is also not noticeable to the third person. However, they care about the students' different aspects of classroom activities. They might outwardly ignore the activities of the students, but they are not completely unknown to them. They silently watch them. This conscious ignoring has come up as a unique strategy to bring the disruptive students back on track, making themselves familiar with the students.

Some of the students, who are disruptive in the classroom, may not respect the teachers. This finding opposes the concept that 'a student respects his or her teacher with 'religious veneration' (Steiner, 1996) without any condition and exception. The teachers' authority may not always remain unquestioned and untested. The informants confirm that they are tested by the students regarding the way they treat them (students). Disruptive students often try to test the authority of the teachers. But the seniority and experience of the teachers make them successful in maintaining authority upon their students. The teachers might ignore such disruption, but they silently keep on monitoring the activities of the students. This technique helps develop familiarity between the teacher and the students. Thus, the teachers' conscious-ignoring can work as a strategy against disruptive behaviors in the classroom. It is justifiable that the teacher's authority is not absolute and honored all the time. It operates in the delicate balance of dynamics of teachers' relationships with their students.

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